

LOGISTICS SYNERGY: MODELS OF UNIVERSITY-ENTERPRISE COOPERATION FOR EDUCATIONAL ELEVATION

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Abstract: *The rapid evolution of the logistics industry necessitates a contemporary approach to training logistics professionals in universities. Over time, the university-enterprise cooperation training model has undergone refinements, revealing its considerable potential and addressing gaps in traditional teaching methods. This paper explores the pivotal role of the university-enterprise cooperation training model in enhancing logistics education within higher education institutions.*

The study examines the significance and functions of this collaborative approach in shaping logistics programs at universities. It delves into how effective university-enterprise partnerships can elevate students' practical skills and bolster their competitiveness in the job market. Additionally, it investigates how such collaborations create mutually beneficial relationships, fostering a win-win scenario for both academia and industry.

The integration of the university-enterprise cooperation training model ushers in fresh opportunities and challenges for the development of logistics education in universities, aligning educational practices with the dynamic needs of the logistics sector.

Keywords: *University-enterprise cooperation, Logistics education, Practical skills, Employment competitiveness, Win-win collaboration*

Introduction

With the rapid development of logistics industry, the training mode of logistics major in universities also needs to keep pace with the times. In the course of years of practice, the university-enterprise cooperation training model has continuously improved the details of university-enterprise cooperation, and also demonstrated the potential of this model, and made up for many shortcomings in traditional teaching. This paper will discuss the significance and function of the university-enterprise cooperation training mode for logistics majors in colleges and universities, and how to effectively improve students' practical ability and employment competitiveness through university-enterprise cooperation, and promote the mutual benefit and win-win situation between university and enterprises. This training will bring new opportunities and challenges to the development of logistics specialty in universities.

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1. A brief description of university-enterprise cooperation mode

University-enterprise cooperation mode refers to the establishment of cooperative relations between universities and enterprises to jointly carry out education training, scientific research cooperation, personnel training and other activities. Under this model, universities can cooperate with enterprises to provide practical teaching, practical training, employment guidance and other services to help students better adapt to the needs of the workplace. Enterprises can cooperate with universities to obtain human resources, technical support, scientific research results, etc., to enhance their competitiveness. The university-enterprise cooperation model can promote the sharing of resources and complementary advantages between universities and enterprises, realize the organic combination of education and industry, provide better employment opportunities for students, and provide more innovation impetus enterprises. At the same time, the university-enterprise cooperation model can also promote the reform university education and teaching, improve the quality of education and teaching effect.

2. The promotion of university-enterprise cooperation model to the development of logistics specialty in universities

3.1 Provide practical opportunities

The university-enterprise cooperation model provides more practical opportunities for college students majoring in logistics, which plays an important role in promoting their career of all, by cooperating with enterprises, students can participate in actual logistics projects and the operation process and practical operation skills of the logistics industry. The theoretical knowledge learned in the classroom can be verified and applied in practice, thus deepening the understanding and mastery of knowledge. Students can personally participate in logistics planning, cargo transportation, warehousing management and other links, understand the specific operation and process of each link, and cultivate practical operation ability and skills. Second, companies provide students with opportunities to interact with industry professionals. Students can communicate and exchange with logistics professionals of enterprises to understand the latest trends and developments in the industry. By working with companies, students can be exposed to real logistics projects and cases, understand practical problems and challenges within the industry, and thus develop problem-solving skills and ways of thinking. Thirdly, the university-enterprise cooperation model can also help students establish contacts and contacts with enterprises. By working with enterprises, students can establish contacts and partnerships with the management and logistics professionals of enterprises. These connections play an important role in promoting students' future employment and career development, and can provide them with more job opportunities and career development platforms.^[1]

To sum up, the university-enterprise cooperation model provides more practical opportunities for college students majoring in logistics, which plays an important role in promoting their career development. By participating in practical logistics projects, students can apply classroom knowledge to practical work and develop practical skills and skills. Exchanges and cooperation with enterprises can help students understand the latest trends and development of the industry, and develop problem-solving skills and ways of thinking. In addition, university-enterprise cooperation can also help students establish contacts and contacts with enterprises, providing more opportunities and platforms for their employment and career development.

3.2 Promote personnel training

Through the enterprise cooperation model, universities can keep abreast of the needs and trends of the logistics industry. As the main participants in the industry, enterprises have a deeper understanding of the development direction and talent needs of the logistics industry. Through cooperation with enterprises, colleges and universities can obtain the latest industry information, so as to adjust the curriculum and teaching content, so that it is more in line with the market demand. In this way, the logistics professionals trained will be more practical and competitive.

In addition, the university-enterprise cooperation model can provide practical cases and experience sharing for college students majoring in logistics. Enterprises can provide real logistics cases to colleges and universities, so that students can analyze and solve in class, so as to improve their practical ability and problem solving ability. At the same time, enterprises can also send professionals to universities to give lectures or practical guidance, and share their experience and experience in the logistics industry with students. In this way, students can better understand the development and employment prospects of the logistics industry and make more informed choices for their career planning.

In short, the university-enterprise cooperation model plays an important role in promoting the talent training of logistics majors in universities. Through cooperation with enterprises, colleges and universities can understand the needs and trends of the logistics industry, adjust the curriculum and teaching content, and train logistics professionals who are more in line with the market demand. At the same time, companies can provide practical cases and experience sharing to help students better understand the development and employment prospects of the logistics industry. The promotion of this cooperation mode will help to improve the quality and competitiveness of logistics professionals in universities and make positive contributions to the development of logistics industry.

3.3 Promote scientific research and innovation

Through cooperation with enterprises, colleges and universities can obtain more practical problems as research materials and have a deep understanding of the actual needs of enterprises in the operation process. Enterprises are faced with various practical problems in the field of logistics, such as supply

chain management, transportation optimization, storage layout, etc. These problems can become scientific research projects of logistics majors in universities. Colleges and universities can cooperate with enterprises to deeply understand the needs of enterprises and carry out targeted scientific research, so as to promote the scientific research and innovation of logistics. Secondly, the university-enterprise cooperation model can provide practical data and resource support for colleges and universities. Enterprises have accumulated a large number of actual data and resources in the field of logistics, which have important reference value for the scientific research work of universities. For example, universities can use the transportation data of enterprises to conduct transportation optimization research, or use the warehousing layout of enterprises to conduct warehousing management research. The support of these actual data and resources can help universities to carry out scientific research and promote the scientific research and innovation of logistics. Finally, the university-enterprise cooperation model can promote the combination of academic research and practical application. The research work of universities is often biased towards academic research, while the needs of enterprises pay more attention to practical application. Through cooperation with enterprises, universities can combine academic research with practical applications, so that scientific research results are closer to actual needs. For example, universities can apply academic research results to the logistics management of enterprises to verify their actual effects. This combination of academic research and practical application can promote the scientific research innovation of logistics profession and make the scientific research results more practical and operable. To sum up, the university-enterprise cooperation model can promote the scientific research and innovation of logistics majors in universities. Through cooperation with enterprises, universities can obtain more practical problems and needs and carry out relevant scientific research projects. At the same time, enterprises can provide practical data and resource support to help universities carry out scientific research. This mode of cooperation can promote the combination of academic research and practical application, and promote the scientific research and innovation of logistics profession.

4. The mode of university-enterprise cooperation training for logistics specialty in universities

4.1 Implement two-way selection

The following methods can be adopted to promote the two-way selection of cooperation training mode between logistics majors and enterprises in universities: First, universities should choose suitable enterprise partners. Colleges and universities can understand the logistics needs and development direction of enterprises through in-depth communication and understanding with enterprises. At the same time, colleges and universities can inspect the logistics management level, technical strength and talent training ability of enterprises to ensure that enterprises have the basic conditions for cooperation

with colleges and universities. Colleges and universities can also refer to the reputation and cooperation history of the enterprise to choose the enterprise to cooperate with. Secondly, enterprises choose the right university partners. Enterprises can understand the teaching level, teachers and practical teaching resources of logistics major in universities and colleges through exchanges and cooperation projects. Enterprises can inspect the logistics laboratories, practice bases and university-enterprise cooperation projects in colleges and universities to evaluate the teaching quality and training ability of logistics majors in colleges and universities. Enterprises can also refer to the academic reputation of colleges and universities and graduate employment situation, choose to cooperate with them. Third, strengthen information sharing and exchange. Universities and enterprises can strengthen information sharing and exchange by establishing regular communication mechanisms. Colleges and universities can introduce the teaching content and training objectives of logistics majors to enterprises, as well as students' practical ability and employment competitiveness. Enterprises can provide universities with the latest development trends and needs of the logistics industry, as well as practical teaching resources. Through information sharing and exchange, the two sides can better understand each other's needs and advantages, providing a better foundation for cooperation. Finally, establish cooperation mechanisms and projects. Universities and enterprises can jointly develop cooperation mechanisms and projects to clarify the responsibilities and rights of both sides. It is possible to establish an internship base for university-enterprise cooperation to provide students with practical opportunities and opportunities to participate in actual projects of enterprises. Joint scientific research projects can be carried out to jointly solve practical problems in the field of logistics. A university-enterprise cooperation training program can be established to train logistics professionals with practical ability and innovative spirit according to the needs of enterprises and the interests of students. Through the above methods, it can realize the two-way choice of cooperation training mode between logistics majors and enterprises, ensure that the two sides of cooperation have a good match in professional fields and teaching resources, and promote the training of logistics professionals and the development of the industry.^[2]

4.2 Carry out practical teaching

Establishing cooperative practice bases. logistics majors in universities and enterprises can jointly establish practice bases to provide internship opportunities for students. Through cooperation with enterprises, students can practice in a real logistics working environment, get exposed to practical operation and problem solving scenarios, and improve practical operation and problem solving abilities. First, carry out practical training courses. Logistics majors in colleges and universities can cooperate with enterprises to carry out practical training courses. Through the actual cases and scenarios provided by the enterprise, students can carry out simulation and practical operation, and exercise practical operation ability and problem solving ability^[3]. Second, organize field visits. Logistics

majors in colleges and universities can organize students to conduct field trips and cooperate with enterprises to visit and study. Students can experience the operation process and management mode of logistics enterprises, understand practical problems and challenges, and improve the ability to solve problems. Third, carry out practical projects. College logistics majors can cooperate with enterprises to carry out practical projects. By working with companies to solve practical problems, students can exercise their practical skills and problem-solving skills, while also providing solutions and innovative ideas for companies. Fourthly, students should be encouraged to participate in practical competitions. College logistics majors can encourage students to participate in various logistics practice competitions. By participating in the competition, students can be exposed to more practical problems and challenges, improve their problem-solving skills and innovation ability, and learn about the gap between themselves and students in other universities through the competition process. Through the above promotion methods, college logistics majors and enterprises can jointly carry out practical teaching activities, provide students with more opportunities for practical operation and problem solving, and improve their practical operation ability and problem solving ability. At the same time, cooperation with enterprises can also promote the in-depth cooperation between universities and enterprises, improve the teaching quality of logistics and students' employment competitiveness.

4.3 Enterprise mentor guidance

Corporate mentors can mentor and develop students in the following ways:

First, make a personalized learning plan. Corporate tutors can develop personalized learning plans according to students' actual situation and career development goals. This can ensure that the learning content and direction of students match the actual needs of enterprises, and improve the learning effect of students. Second, provide practical opportunities. Corporate mentors can provide hands-on opportunities for students to learn and practice their acquired knowledge and skills in a real work environment. Through practice, students can better understand and apply the theoretical knowledge they have learned and improve their practical operation ability. Third, give regular evaluations and feedback. Corporate tutors can assess students on a regular basis to see how they are progressing and what their problems are. At the same time, give students timely feedback and suggestions to help them improve and enhance their learning ability and work performance. Fourth, provide career planning guidance. Corporate mentors can help students with career planning and guide them in developing personal career development goals and plans. By understanding students' interests and strengths, corporate mentors can provide them with relevant career advice and development paths to help them better plan their career development. Fifth, good communication and cooperative relations: Corporate tutors can establish good communication and cooperative relations with students to promote interaction and exchange between the two sides. By working closely with students, corporate mentors

can better understand students' needs and problems and address and support their learning and development in a timely manner.

4.4 University enterprise joint evaluation

First, establish a university-enterprise cooperation evaluation mechanism. universities and enterprises can jointly develop evaluation standards and evaluation methods to ensure the objectivity and fairness of evaluation. The contents and standards of evaluation can be clarified by formulating evaluation indicators and evaluation forms. Second, carry out practical evaluation. universities and enterprises can jointly evaluate students' practical performance. Through practical activities such as internship and training, students can show their professional ability and practical operation ability. universities and enterprises can jointly evaluate students' practical performance, including practical ability, work attitude, teamwork and other aspects. Third, comprehensive quality evaluation. In addition to academic performance and practical performance, universities and enterprises can also jointly evaluate the overall quality of students. Comprehensive quality includes students' comprehensive ability, innovation ability, communication ability, leadership ability and so on. Through comprehensive quality assessment, students' ability and potential can be more comprehensively understood. Fourth, regular evaluation and feedback. universities and businesses can conduct regular evaluations and feedback to keep abreast of students' learning and development. Students can be provided with accurate career development guidance and advice through regular interviews and evaluation reports. At the same time, universities and enterprises can also adjust and improve training plans and teaching content according to the evaluation results. Fifth, establish a university-enterprise cooperation evaluation team. universities and enterprises can jointly form evaluation teams, which are composed of university teachers and enterprise professionals. The evaluation team can jointly develop evaluation standards and methods, and participate in the evaluation process to ensure the professionalism and authority of the evaluation.

5. Conclusion

Through the university-enterprise cooperation training model for logistics majors in colleges and universities, students can get in touch with actual logistics operations during university, and improve their practical ability and professional quality. At the same time, the participation of enterprises can also provide more internship and employment opportunities for students, and increase employment competitiveness. The implementation of university-enterprise cooperation training model can not only meet the needs of enterprises for logistics talents, but also improve the teaching quality of logistics majors and the comprehensive quality of students. The successful implementation of this cooperation mode requires close cooperation and joint efforts between universities and enterprises to train more excellent logistics talents and contribute to the development of the logistics industry.

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References

- Qian Yuanling(2022). Research on the path of cultivating cross-border e-commerce talents through university-enterprise Cooperation [J]. Chinese and Foreign Corporate Culture,(08):pp.232-234. [2] Sun Wenjuan(2021). Cultivating Application-oriented Talents through university-enterprise Cooperation from the perspective of Artisan Spirit [J]. Modern Enterprise,(10):pp.156-157.*
- Kuang Hong(2016). Teaching Reform and Practice of university-Enterprise Cooperation in Cultivating Applied talents -- A case study of Logistics Management major of Chongqing Second Normal University [J]. Journal of Chongqing Second Normal University,(06):pp.105-108+167.*

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